

Differential Growth of the Mussels *Perna perna* and *Perna viridis* (Bivalvia: Mytilidae) in Suspended Culture in the Golfo de Cariaco, Venezuela

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Abstract

We evaluated the growth of mussels *Perna perna* and *Perna viridis* in suspended culture in the Golfo de Cariaco in Venezuela. Juveniles were cultured for up to 13 mo on cultch strings suspended from longline, with monthly sampling for determination of shell length and dry weights of shell and soft tissues. Water temperature, oxygen, salinity, chlorophyll *a*, seston, and shell fouling were also monitored. In both species, growth during the first 5 mo (the stratification period in the region) was slow. Subsequently, the onset of the coastal upwelling period (November/December) generated lower temperatures and higher plankton levels, correlated with higher growth rates, particularly in *P. perna*, which by the end of the experiment had reached a mean length 1.3-fold greater than that of *P. viridis* (95.3 ± 7.91 vs. 73.3 ± 6.99 mm) together with a 1.9-fold greater somatic tissue. Likewise, reproductive activity differed between the two species, *P. perna* showing a higher gonad development and its reproductive activity starting earlier than that of *P. viridis*. Our results show that *P. perna* presents higher growth and survival than *P. viridis* in suspension culture, a fact related to a greater tolerance to the environmental characteristics of the Golfo de Cariaco.

Bivalve mollusks are among the most economically important groups in mariculture, with many species showing low production costs and high profitability. Among the most widely cultivated species are the mussels, characterized by their high rates of filtration, growth, and fecundity. Indeed, mussel culture is one of the most important aquaculture activities worldwide. Major producers include China, Thailand,

and Spain, with the most widely cultivated species belonging to the genera *Mytilus* (*Mytilus edulis*, *Mytilus galloprovincialis*, and *Mytilus trossulus*) and *Perna* (*Perna perna*, *Perna viridis*, and *Perna canaliculus*) (Hickman 1992; Labarta et al. 2004).

The mussel most extensively cultivated in Venezuela is the brown mussel, *P. perna*, a species originating in Africa and South Asia (Agard et al. 1992) that has become established on the South American Atlantic coast from Uruguay

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to the northern coast of Venezuela (Lodeiros et al. 1999). One of the factors permitting the establishment of this species on the northeastern Venezuelan coast was possibly the coastal annual upwelling in this region, which generates conditions similar to those seen in this species' subtropical region of origin. These conditions have allowed *P. perna* to form extensive natural stocks and indeed become one of Venezuela's most important fishery resources (Benítez 1968; Carvajal 1969; Benítez and Okuda 1971; Acuña 1977; Lodeiros et al. 2006). At the start of the 1990s, the green mussel, *P. viridis*, became established on the eastern Venezuelan coast (Agard et al. 1992), rapidly colonizing different coastal ecosystems, reflecting its tolerance to the temperature and salinity variations occurring annually in these waters (Rylander et al. 1996; Segnini et al. 1998; Segnini 2003). This species has a wide geographical range and its distribution can be considered both tropical and subtropical: it originated in the Indo-Pacific region, extending longitudinally from the Persian Gulf to the southwestern Pacific and latitudinally from southeast Japan to Papua New Guinea (Cheung 1991).

Currently, on the northeastern Venezuelan coast, there are thus two species of mussel, *P. perna* and *P. viridis*, forming extensive populations that together constitute an important fishery resource (Lodeiros et al. 2006). None of the species is currently widely cultivated, although there is some small-scale cultivation of *P. perna*. With a view to identifying the most suitable species for suspension culture in this region, the present study conducted culture trials aimed at contrasting the growth of these two species in the face of environmental variation in the Golfo de Cariaco.

Materials and Methods

Spats of *P. perna* and *P. viridis* were collected from natural beds in Guayacán (Araya Peninsula) by scuba diving to depths of 1–2 m and then transported in isothermal containers to the Estación Hidrobiológica de Turpialito in the Golfo de Cariaco (Fig. 1). Here, the spats with maximum homogeneous shell length were selected (*P. perna*: 35.5 ± 3.16 mm; *P. viridis*:

FIGURE 1. Maps showing the location of the study site in Turpialito, Golfo de Cariaco, Venezuela.

34.3 ± 3.99 mm; no significant differences were found between the two species, ANOVA, $P > 0.05$).

In July 2002, a total of 72 cultch strings of 1 m (36 for each species) were seeded with 30 mussels each and then suspended to a depth of about 2 m from a 100-m buoyed longline placed about 30 m from the shore. The seeding was performed manually with a mesh specifically designed for this task and sufficiently strong to support seeds for 24–48 h (long enough to allow byssal attachment to the rope).

At monthly intervals over the next 13 mo (July 2002 to July 2003), three cultch strings of each species were sampled from the longline. We then determined dorsoventral shell length (using digital calipers, precision ± 0.01 mm) and dry weight (by drying to constant weight at 70 C and weighing with precision ± 0.001 g) of shell, muscle, gonadal lobes, remaining somatic tissues, and the mass of fouling organisms on the shells.

At weekly intervals, we collected triplicate water samples from the study site in a 2-L Niskin bottle from which 250 mL subsamples were analyzed for dissolved oxygen content (Winkler method) and salinity (by refractometry, precision $\pm 1\%$). Other subsamples (1 L) were used for estimation of plankton levels: the subsample was first filtered (153- μm pore size) to remove macroplankton and other large particles and then analyzed for chlorophyll *a* concentration (phytoplanktonic biomass) and seston concentration (total, organic, and inorganic). These analyses were performed after filtration with Whatman GF/F filters (0.7- μm pore size) using a Millipore vacuum filtration apparatus. Chlorophyll *a* was determined by standard spectrophotometric methods. Seston concentration was determined gravimetrically as per Strickland and Parsons (1972).

Length–weight relations (shell length to shell weight, to somatic tissue weight, and to total weight) were evaluated by simple regression methods and slope comparison between species as per Zar (1984). We used a two-factor (species and time) ANOVA to compare growth parameters (shell length, dry mass of shell, gonad, muscle, and remaining somatic tissues), dry mass of fouling on shells, and survival. As the two-factor ANOVAs were significant ($P < 0.05$) for both factors, we applied a one-factor ANOVA to each species, followed by a Duncan a posteriori analysis in order to show the significant differences ($P < 0.05$) in the time factor. The Shapiro–Wilks' *W* test was applied to verify that the measurements of body components did not deviate from a normal distribution. An arcsine transformation was performed to proportion values (survival) in order to normalize the data according to

recommendations by Zar (1984). In each ANOVA, the distribution of the variance residues showed an acceptable homogeneity.

Results

Water temperature peaked around 30 C in September 2002 and then declined gradually to a minimum of about 22.0–22.5 C in January 2003 (Fig. 2A). Between February and mid-March 2003, temperature remained below 24 C and then increased to 26 C by the end of April, remaining around this level to the end of the study period. Dissolved oxygen content showed a declining trend over the study period but always remained above 4 mg/L (Fig. 2B).

FIGURE 2. Water temperature (A), dissolved oxygen content (B), and salinity (C) at the study site over the experimental period. In the case of dissolved oxygen, values shown are means for $n = 3$ samples on each sampling day; vertical bars show SDs.

Salinity showed a similar pattern, varying over a range of about 34–38‰ (Fig. 2C).

Phytoplankton biomass, as indicated by chlorophyll *a* concentration, showed the opposite pattern to temperature (Fig. 3A): this is normal in the study area, reflecting the coastal upwelling phenomena because of wind regimes in this region (see Moigis 1986; Lodeiros and Himmelman 2000). During periods of higher temperature (mid-August to end of November 2002, and April 2003), chlorophyll *a* levels were below 1 µg/L, while during the remaining periods of lower temperature, chlorophyll *a* levels were above 4 µg/L. Similar tendencies were observed for total seston concentration and

FIGURE 3. Chlorophyll *a* concentration (A), total seston concentration (B), and seston organic content (C) during the experimental period. Values shown are means for $n = 3$ samples on each sampling day; vertical bars show SDs.

seston organic content: seston concentration was highest (40–60 mg/L) during January and February (Fig. 3B), coinciding with the period of highest seston organic content (>80%; Fig. 3C) and lowest water temperature.

The dry mass of fouling in *P. viridis* increased significantly in November and May ($P < 0.05$), followed by a steady decrease until July. In *P. perna*, the significant increases in fouling mass ($P < 0.05$) were in January and April, this species reaching a higher mass value than *P. viridis* by the end of the experiment (Fig. 4).

Shell length–weight relations (shell length to shell weight, to somatic tissue weight, and to total weight) were statistically significant ($P < 0.001$), although the coefficients of determination varied greatly from $r^2 = 0.53$ to 0.90. The slope of the relations was significantly higher ($P < 0.001$) in *P. perna* than in *P. viridis*.

The ANOVAs revealed significant differences ($P < 0.05$) in all growth parameters for both species and time factors. The tests confirmed a greater growth for *P. perna*, although both species attained growth variability with regard to the time factor.

Both species showed similar growth in shell length over the first 5 mo (July to November 2002; Fig. 5A). Subsequently, the growth curves diverged, with *P. viridis* showing low growth rates in contrast with *P. perna*, which showed significant increases ($P < 0.05$) until mid-December 2002, a period of nongrowth ensuing at this time up until the beginning of

FIGURE 4. Fouling mass on the shell of *Perna perna* and *P. viridis* over the experimental period. Values shown are means; vertical bars show SDs.

FIGURE 5. Growth of *Perna perna* and *P. viridis* over the experimental period in terms of shell length (A), dry weight of shell (B), muscle (C), remaining somatic tissues (D), and gonad (E). Values shown are means; vertical bars show SDs.

February, when growth was resumed with higher rates ($P < 0.05$) until the end of the experiment, when this species reached a mean length 1.3-fold greater than that obtained by *P. viridis* (95.3 ± 7.91 vs. 73.3 ± 6.99 mm, respectively). Shell dry weight showed the same trend (Fig. 5B), with *P. perna* reaching a final weight (31.0 ± 5.74 g) 2.5-fold greater than that of *P. viridis* (12.5 ± 3.11 g).

In contrast with shell growth, the growth rates for muscle and other soft tissues (Figs. 5C, D) were very similar in the two species until March 2003 (the eighth month of the experiment), when the curves diverged, with *P. perna* showing a higher growth rate ($P < 0.05$). By the end of the experiment, *P. perna* had reached

a 1.9-fold higher muscle weight and a 4.2-fold higher nonmuscle somatic tissue weight than the corresponding parameters in *P. viridis*.

Likewise, gonad production differed between the two species (Fig. 5E). Growth in *P. perna* began between October and November 2003, a swift and significant increase ($P < 0.05$) being evident until mid-December, when the first gonad maturation occurred. The subsequent rapid drop in gonad mass suggests that spawning took place between mid-December and mid-January, with a period of intermediate production elapsing until the end of April 2003 and a subsequent period of fast-paced gonad weight increase that continued until the end of the experiment. In contrast, *P. viridis* commenced

gonad production at the end of December 2002, with a small increase in gonad mass until January 2003 (not a very rapid increase as in *P. perna*). A gradual decline in gonad weight began then until the end of April, followed by a slight but significant increase until May ($P < 0.05$) and by a final period of constant weight until the end of the study. Gonad weight in both species, particularly over the last 3 mo, showed high dispersions relative to the mean, suggesting that there may have been some spawning activity during this period. At the end of the study period, when peak gonad weights were observed in both species, *P. perna* showed a gonad weight fivefold greater than that of *P. viridis* (1.5 ± 0.54 vs. 0.3 ± 0.01 g, respectively). This difference is likewise seen in the gonadosomatic index in relation to shell size (Fig. 6), the index reaching values of about 70% in some individuals of *P. perna* (notably individuals about 65 mm long) versus only about 40% in *P. viridis*. In both species, gonadosomatic index values began to show interindividual variability from 38 to 40 mm body length, suggesting that this is about the minimum length for reproductive activity.

Survival rates were higher in *P. perna* but in general not significantly higher than in *P. viridis* (Fig. 7). The monthly survival rate was 80% or more in both species over the first 12 mo, while in the last month (July 2003), the survival rate dropped dramatically to 50% in *P. perna* and 30% in *P. viridis*. These final survival rates were significantly different ($P < 0.05$).

FIGURE 6. Gonadosomatic index (gonad/somatic weight, %) relate to shell length for *Perna perna* and *P. viridis*.

FIGURE 7. Survival of *Perna perna* and *P. viridis* over the experimental period. Values shown are means, and vertical bars show SDs.

Discussion

In both species, the shell growth and somatic tissue growth were slow over the first 5 mo of the study period. This can probably be attributed to physiological stress because of the high temperatures and low food availability between July and November 2002, a period characterized by stratification of the water column in the Golfo de Cariaco (Okuda et al. 1978; Ferraz-Reyes 1987). In the Golfo de Cariaco and other tropical areas affected by coastal upwelling phenomena, this period can be considered critical for mussel cultivation. Similar responses have been reported for other cultured bivalves in the study region, including *Argopecten nucleus* (Lodeiros et al. 1993), *Euvola ziczac* (Lodeiros and Himmelman 1994, 2000), and *Nodidipeten nodosus* (Lodeiros et al. 1998; Acosta et al. 2000).

After the period of slow growth, and despite high variability in some determinations, *P. perna* consistently showed faster growth than *P. viridis*, suggesting a more adaptability to culture condition in the region. In both species, the increases in shell and tissue weight coincided with the start of the coastal upwelling (November/December 2002) that occurs annually in the Golfo de Cariaco, an occurrence that particularly favored *P. perna*. This period is characterized by low temperatures and high food availability, with high seston concentrations that may provide an additional source of food for mussels; indeed, *P. viridis* has been shown to ingest seston with high efficacy (Hawkins

et al. 1998; Wong and Cheung 2001). There is a clear need for studies that allow evaluation of the effect of food on the growth of these two species, under conditions of variability in the availability of seston with respect to other food types, with the aim of evaluating whether *P. viridis* is likely to show acceptable yields in specific areas of the Golfo de Cariaco. In this connection, field studies of suspension and bottom culture would be sufficient because the environment of these systems already shows variations in seston quality and quantity (Hunauld et al. 2005).

It has been demonstrated that the physiological adjustments to which organisms are subject may be dependent on food availability in the environment, and this behavior has been reported for *M. galloprovincialis* (Navarro et al. 1996) and *P. viridis* (Hawkins et al. 1998). In the present study, we did not observe this behavior because in both species, variations in growth pattern were possibly modulated by temperature, with slower growth at lower temperatures, particularly in *P. viridis*. Plankton, although generally available, had at most a secondary effect because neither phytoplankton biomass nor total seston concentration or seston organic content was strongly correlated with growth. These findings suggest that food was not a limiting factor for growth.

Unlike temperature and food availability, oxygen concentration and salinity remained elevated and with little variability over the study period (5.5–7.0 mg/L and 36–38‰, respectively). These concentrations are within a normal range for physiological activities in molluscan bivalve (Griffiths and Griffiths 1987; Segnini et al. 1998; Segnini 2003) and thus are unlikely to have affected growth.

Both species, particularly *P. perna*, showed reduced somatic tissue weight and a lack of shell growth from about the fifth or sixth month of culture, possibly related to endogenous factors having to do with processes of gametogenesis and spawning, reflecting energy transfer and modulated by environmental factors like temperature and food availability. Bivalve gametogenesis is a process requiring high energy expenditure, and different species adopt

different strategies to deal with this: for example, some use energy obtained directly from food, while others use energy stored in tissues (Barber and Blake 1991). In the case of *P. perna*, we suggest that energy stored in somatic tissues (muscle, mantle, and digestive gland) may be redirected to the gonads, in view of the negative correlation observed between somatic tissue weight and gonad weight, implying a conservative reproductive strategy as suggested by Bayne (1976). This type of strategy is frequent in bivalves of temperate regions (Gabott and Bayne 1973) and has also been reported in two species that have been cultured experimentally in the Golfo de Cariaco, *E. ziczac* and *Pinna carnea* (Lodeiros and Himmelman 2000). In the case of *P. viridis*, spawning coincided with low food availability in April and with water temperatures over 26 C, typical of tropical regions; subsequently, gonad weight remained constant, although with a slight increase at the end of the study period. According to Walter (1982), *P. viridis* from the coast of Philippines spawns throughout the year without any seasonal peak. In the present study, with higher environmental variation, reproduction may have been affected by the low water temperature, reducing formation of both reproductive and somatic tissue and thus influencing transfer of energy substrates to reproductive tissues. This is in line with Lee (1988), who found that in *P. viridis*, the key determinant of the reproductive cycle is temperature, with 24 C being the critical threshold. As a result, the brusque changes in temperature seen in the Golfo de Cariaco (from 26 to 24 C, or from 23 to 25 C, within only a few days) may inhibit this species' reproductive cycle.

Shell fouling (because of growth of filter-feeding organisms on the shell) may negatively influence growth by hindering shell opening and closing and/or by competing for food (Lesser et al. 1992; Lodeiros and Himmelman 1996). In the present study, fouling had little impact on the growth of either species, possibly because of the vertical position adopted in suspended culture, which may reduce effects on shell opening and closing (see Lodeiros 2002). However, even in suspended culture, fouling may have

negative consequences, notably by increasing overall shell weight and thus the risk that the shell will become detached from the cultch string; this may indeed explain the high mortality observed at the end of our study period. The somewhat higher survival rate of *P. perna* during this period may reflect better byssal attachment than in *P. viridis* (pers. obs.). An alternative hypothesis that could explain the high mortality at the end of experiment was the possible effect of low oxygen and salinity concentration in this period; however, the values of these variables appear far away of lethal levels in marine bivalves (Bernard 1983).

Shell length growth by *P. perna* in the present study was faster than recorded in previous studies in this region (Vélez 1971; Acuña 1977) but similar to that reported by Poza (1984) and León et al. (1998) in Charagato Bay (Nueva Esparta state, Venezuela); these latter authors reported growth to 90 mm within 1 yr. Also, the growth of *P. perna* was similar in Brazil when Márquez et al. (1991) reported 60 mm in 7 mo. In the case of *P. viridis*, different growth rates have been reported under different culture systems in various coastal locations in India, ranging from 80 to 85 mm (Sreenivasan et al. 1989) and over 90 mm in estuarine waters within 1 yr.

The growth of *P. viridis* in the present study was much slower than the one seen in the last studies reported, supporting the hypothesis that *P. viridis* is under stress in suspended culture in the Golfo de Cariaco; thus, this production system would not seem to be effective for *P. viridis* in this region, although bottom culture might be a viable alternative.

In a recent study in the same study area and over the same period of the year, Urbano et al. (2005) found less growth in both *P. perna* and *P. viridis* than that observed in the present study (shell lengths of 77.8 and 71.2 mm in 10 mo, respectively). These authors attributed these low growth rates to stress because of the shellfish being cultured in oyster baskets, which reduce food particle inflow and provide a microhabitat for mussel predators. This suggests that suspended rope culture has certain advantages with respect to basket culture or at least suspended basket culture.

Our results show that *P. perna* presents a higher rate of growth than *P. viridis* in suspension culture, a phenomenon that could be related to a greater tolerance to the environmental characteristics of the Golfo de Cariaco.

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